

Project-based learning: Design and development of a service-learning project in Statistics

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Abstract

Service-learning (SL) is a methodology widely used in some universities, whose purpose is for students to acquire knowledge and skills while doing a service to the community.

A SL project was proposed to students of Industrial Engineering to collaborate with students of the degrees in Statistics and Labor Relations of the University of Salamanca. The goal of the activity was to develop teamwork in such a way that each team included students from the different degrees.

The University of Salamanca has institutionalized the SL projects and each year there is a call to all teachers. A group of these teachers who teach statistics, together with the Spanish Network of Entities Against Leukemia and Blood Diseases (AELCLÉS), proposed the project “Learning Statistics in Collaboration with the Community”, with the aim of connecting university teaching of statistics with practical applications in the community, highlighting its value in improving the quality of life of hematological patients.

From an interdisciplinary approach, this project addresses challenges such as data cleaning and the generation of statistical reports through descriptive and inferential analysis, using statistical tools such as R, SPSS and Excel.

The SL project highlights the benefits of integrating the Sustainable Development Goals into the teaching of STEM disciplines, demonstrating how mathematics can be transformed into an essential tool for turning data into meaningful knowledge. This approach is particularly relevant in collaboration with the AELCLÉS association, whose work focuses on improving the quality of life of haematology patients and their caregivers. Through statistical analysis, data-driven solutions are provided that enable organizations with a strong social commitment to optimize their support and care programs.

In addition, some of the learning outcomes achieved by students are improved critical thinking and technical competence, along with the social impact of collaboration, creating a bridge between technical knowledge and its application in real life.

Introduction

In recent years, universities have incorporated active learning methodologies that allow students to develop academic and professional competences through direct experience.

Among these methodologies, Service-Learning (SL) has established itself as a pedagogical strategy that integrates academic learning with the provision of community service, fostering civic engagement and social responsibility among students (Jacoby, 2015; McNatt, 2020). This methodology is usually developed following well-defined stages, ranging from the identification of community needs to the evaluation and recognition of results, as Queiruga-Dios et al. (2023) point out.

Several studies have highlighted the benefits of this methodology in the university environment, both at an academic and personal level, favouring the acquisition of technical and transversal competences, the improvement of academic performance and the development of social values (Muñoz-Medina et al., 2021). In the specific case of technical and scientific degrees, ApS allows students to apply the knowledge acquired in real situations, while contributing to the improvement of the quality of life of certain social groups, as occurs in projects linked to the health or social fields. This application in technical and quantitative contexts is still rare, as pointed out by Queiruga-Dios et al. (2021), who estimate that less than 1% of the studies on P2P in Scopus are related to mathematics.

Interdisciplinary work has become an essential element in contemporary university education, especially in social projects, where the complexity of the problems to be addressed requires the collaboration of professionals from different areas of knowledge (Bowland et al., 2015). This approach makes it possible to integrate different methodological and conceptual perspectives, favouring a more complete and enriching analysis of social reality.

This is the context of the project carried out in collaboration with ASCOL (Association against Leukaemia and Blood Diseases) and the Spanish Network of Organisations Against Leukaemia and Blood Diseases (AELCLÉS). The initiative consisted of the cleaning and analysis of a database from surveys of haematological patients and their carers, with the aim of improving the care and support offered to this group. The work has been developed through the participation of students from different university degrees (Industrial Engineering, Statistics and Labour Relations and Human Resources), integrating technical and social skills through an interdisciplinary approach.

The main objective of this paper is to analyse and present a Service-Learning (SL) experience developed with the active participation of students from different degrees, both from engineering and other disciplines. This interdisciplinary approach has enriched the learning process by integrating diverse perspectives and knowledge, fostering meaningful and collaborative learning. In addition, the project has promoted the social commitment of the students by involving them in solving real problems with an impact on local communities or organisations. Through this experience, the aim is not only to strengthen specific competencies in each discipline, but also transversal skills such as teamwork, communication and ethical responsibility, which are essential for training professionals committed to society.

The SL experience involved statistical analysis of real data from haematological patients and carers, promoting technical skills through applied learning. The project also generated useful knowledge to optimise social and healthcare resources for this group, highlighting specific needs and proposing concrete improvements. In this way, it contributed to the advancement of several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), in particular SDG 3 (Health and Wellbeing), SDG 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 10 (Reducing Inequalities), aligning academic work with current global challenges.

Method of Investigation

Thirty students from the University of Salamanca, from different degrees: Degree in Industrial Engineering (specialising in Mechanics, Electronics and Automation, and Electricity), Degree in Statistics and Degree in Labour Relations and Human Resources, participated voluntarily. They were divided into 6 groups, with 5 members in each, all of them interdisciplinary.

The activity was carried out during the first four-month period of the academic year 2024-2025 (September 2024-January 2025), in collaboration with ASCOL and AELCLÉS. The entire process was carried out entirely in the facilities of the University of Salamanca, using both conventional classrooms and computer rooms equipped with the necessary resources and statistical software (Excel, SPSS and R).

The project was divided into four phases, described below:

Phase 0: Introduction (September-October 2024)

An initial session was held with all the students and teaching staff involved and the president of ASCOL to explain what the APS project consisted of. During this session, the questionnaire used, the study population, the sample, the variables selected and the database, which was divided into five sub-bases for subsequent analysis, were explained.

Phase 1: Constitution of interdisciplinary working groups (October 2024)

Working teams were organised with students from the different degrees involved, ensuring an interdisciplinary approach. Each group assumed specific responsibilities and was coordinated by a lecturer. Each team was assigned one of the five sub-bases, with the following themes:

- **Group 1:** Diagnosed disease type, previous exposure to radiation or chemicals, family history and involvement in novel therapies.
- **Group 2:** Current treatment status, type of treatment, compliance with treatment received and side effects.
- **Group 3:** Emotional reaction to diagnosis, medical information seeking and use of information resources.
- **Group 4:** Immunological status, history of serious infections, hygiene precautions and emotional health after the illness.

- **Group 5:** Current emotional state and perception of care received during the disease process.
- **Group 6:** Multivariate analysis of all the previous bases, integrating all the variables to identify significant relationships and characteristic profiles within the group of patients.

Phase 2: Debugging, data analysis and reporting (November-December 2024)

The teams conducted an initial debugging process, identifying and correcting errors or inconsistencies in the data. They then organised the sub-bases into formats suitable for statistical analysis and selected the most appropriate techniques for each specific objective. Excel, SPSS and R software were used to develop descriptive, inferential and even multivariate analyses. Each group produced a preliminary report with the main results obtained.

Phase 3: Presentation of results (December 2024-January 2025)

The final reports and conclusions of each group were presented in person to the members of ASCOL, a member of AELCLÉS, in a session held at the University of Salamanca. During this session, the most relevant findings were presented and proposals for improvement aimed at optimising care and support for haematological patients and their carers were formulated.

Phase 4: Evaluation of both teachers, students and ASCOL members involved in the project.

The last phase of the project focused on the evaluation of the experience by the different agents involved: teachers, students and ASCOL, also representing AELCLÉS. As for the teaching staff, a joint assessment was carried out based on the participation and monitoring of pupils throughout the project. The teaching staff carried out a joint assessment based on students' participation and project follow-up.

The students participated voluntarily in a questionnaire designed to gather their perception of the project's development, the learning acquired and the usefulness of the experience. A service-learning rubric adapted from international models was applied before and after the project to evaluate its formative impact. To this end, two questionnaires were applied: one before the start of the experience and the other at the end of the ApS project, in order to evaluate the formative impact of the intervention. This rubric makes it possible to identify whether the activity carried out corresponds to quality service-learning, based on seven key criteria that integrate the academic context with a commitment to social practice. The results obtained were favourable, highlighting aspects such as practical learning, teamwork and the social value of the project. The responses collected show a high degree of satisfaction with the experience, as well as a perceived improvement in technical skills, communication, critical thinking and sensitivity to health-related social issues.

Finally, the members of ASCOL and AELCLÉS also carried out a qualitative evaluation of the results, focusing on the usefulness of the information generated to support decision-making and to propose improvements in the care and accompaniment of haematological patients and their carers. The association expressly stated the relevance and applicability

of the analyses carried out, positively valuing both the rigour of the data and the social sensitivity shown by the participating students.

Results

The Service-Learning project developed made it possible to gather a comprehensive assessment of the experience by the different agents involved: students from the different degree courses taking part, the teaching staff responsible and the president of the ASCOL association. Through satisfaction surveys, self-evaluations and direct observation during the final presentations, it was possible to identify the educational, personal and social scope of this activity. The following are the main evaluations according to the degrees and roles involved.

In the case of the Degree in Industrial Engineering, a total of 13 students took part, some of whom had personal links with the subject addressed, such as the close experience of a friend affected by leukaemia. However, face-to-face participation in the joint activities was lower than expected, a circumstance mainly attributed to the location of the Engineering campus, 72 km away from the faculties of Statistics and Social Sciences, which made face-to-face collaboration difficult despite the students' familiarity with online work. The final presentation was attended by only two students from this degree programme. In spite of the low level of participation, the work was positively evaluated, highlighting the practical application of the statistics subject, which usually does not attract the interest of engineering students. It was pointed out that this type of initiative improves motivation, broadens university perspectives beyond academics and facilitates the acquisition of relevant competences for their professional future.

The nine first-year students of the Degree in Statistics showed notable involvement and a proactive attitude. They took responsibility for data debugging and organisation, demonstrating technical rigour and teamwork skills unusual for their academic level. The experience was highly valued by the students themselves, who were not only confronted with real and complex databases but also became aware of the harshness of the social reality they reflected. They pointed out that, thanks to this project, they were able to carry out real field work, consolidate their knowledge and apply new tools for data cleaning and processing, which enabled them to see at an early stage the practical dimension and social value of their discipline. From the teaching point of view, their maturity, technical rigour and sensitivity to the context were underlined, especially valuing their role as a link between the raw information and its statistical analysis, favouring interdisciplinary cohesion with the students of the other participating degrees.

Twelve students from the Degree in Labour Relations and Human Resources participated. Their involvement was remarkable from the very first moment, showing a very receptive attitude and interest in the project from its initial presentation. Most of them attended the informative meetings and the formal presentation of the project, participating in an active and committed way. Throughout the implementation, they expressed their doubts and concerns on several occasions, always oriented towards rigorously complying with the proposed objectives, which indicates a reflective and responsible attitude towards the proposed challenges. They revealed that they had some initial problems with the distribution and assignment of tasks, which they finally resolved. Their assessment of the experience was very positive, highlighting both the learning acquired and the opportunity to contribute to an initiative with a clear social impact. In this sense, they expressed their

wish that their work could, to some extent, have a favourable impact on the quality of life of haematological patients and their carers. The teaching team particularly valued their ability to connect the disciplinary knowledge of the degree with the human and organisational needs of the healthcare context, as well as their sensitivity to the welfare of the people involved.

The 4th-year students of the Statistics degree, the only group from the same program, applied multivariate techniques learned during their studies. Although the data limited the use of some methods, they chose the most suitable ones and complemented previous analyses, bringing a more advanced statistical perspective.

Finally, the president of ASCOL, who also spoke on behalf of AELCLÉS, gave a very positive assessment of the development and results of the project, highlighting the responsible and committed attitude of the students, as well as the usefulness of the reports produced. He stressed that the students were able to treat the data with sensitivity and rigour, aware that behind each figure there were personal stories. Moreover, although some of the results did not match the initial expectations of ASCOL and AELCLÉS, this made it possible to identify aspects that merited further research. Both the association and the network highlighted the importance of this type of collaboration in bringing the university closer to the real needs of the community.

Overall, the ApS experience was valued as highly enriching, allowing the integration of academic learning, social engagement and interdisciplinary work in a real context, aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals and with the values of higher education committed to social transformation.

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